

Combinatory Method for Determining Lattice Parameters Using Python

Jones Leite Soares^{1,*}

Jobson Luiz Leite Soares^{2,**}

¹PhD degree for Science by Institute of Chemistry (University of São Paulo). Jones Leite Soares has extensive experience in chemical analysis and material science, with prior affiliations to Centro Universitário Braz Cubas.

² Undergraduate for Administration by University of Mogi das Cruzes (UMC) and systems analyst.

*e-mail: soares.jones@aluno.ifsp.edu.br

**e-mail: jobson.soares65@gmail.com

Abstract. The method for determining the lattice parameters of a crystalline structure is based on combining of n diffractogram peaks with the p unknown parameters of the structures. The equations combined in systems of equations p to p are those that relate the lattice parameters and the hkl indices with the interplanar distance. The technique to solve the structure of the seven known crystalline systems used the Python language to develop seven small codes, one for each structure type. The determined values of the lattice parameters were compared with a database and the differences were discussed.

Keywords: crystal structure; lattice parameters; Python.

INTRODUCTION

According to the International Union of Crystallography,^[1] a unit cell is the parallelepiped built on the vectors **a**, **b**, and **c** of a direct lattice crystallographic basis. These vectors, which define the cells, are known as crystallographic axes.^[2] Lattice parameters are quantities that describe the unit cell of a crystalline system. They are used to characterize the arrangement of atoms and ions in a three-dimensional crystalline solid. These parameters are the lengths of the lattice vectors, representing the distances between adjacent atoms or ions. These lengths are generally represented by the letters “*a*”, “*b*” and “*c*” and can be the same or different from each other along the three orthogonal axes of the crystal. The lattice parameters (figure 1) also refer to the angles between the lattice vectors and are commonly represented by “*α*”, “*β*” and “*γ*”^[2]: *α* is the angle between lengths *b* and *c*; *β* is the angle between lengths *c* and *a*; and *γ* is the angle between lengths *a* and *b*.

Figure 1. Unit Cell.^[2]

These parameters are fundamental for understanding crystalline structures of materials. They directly influence the physical and chemical properties of these materials, including mechanical, optical, electronic, and thermal properties.^{[3][4][5][6]} Furthermore, lattice parameters are used in diffraction analysis techniques such as x-ray diffraction to determine the crystal structure of materials,^[7] and are fundamental in areas such as crystallography and

materials science. For this reason, it is important to determine the lattice structure with the greatest precision. [8]

Equation (1) [9] defines the perpendicular distances between successive planes (d_{hkl}), also known as interplanar distances, for any of the crystalline systems, where h , k and l are integers that define the orientation of a plane of atoms in a unit cell, and the hkl notation designates a family of planes:

$$\frac{1}{d_{hkl}^2} = |h\mathbf{a} + k\mathbf{b} + l\mathbf{c}|^2 \quad (1)$$

From the development of equation (1) it is possible to formulate interplanar distances for each crystalline system.

The Rietveld refinement method [10] is based on the least squares method, [11] which is a standard technique in statistics and optimization used to find the best approximation of a set of equations.

There are several computational methods, the use of artificial intelligence and machine learning that allow the determination of lattice parameters. [12],[13],[14],[15],[16],[17],[18] The Python programming language is used for simulations in the determination of crystalline structures based on density functional theory. [19] The method called Cramer-Cohen is used to determine the lattice parameters of cubic, tetragonal and hexagonal structures with the help of Python or Excel software. [20],[21],[22]

We will describe here the combinatorial method, and its implementation based on structural data reported in the literature with the help of the Python language.

COMBINATORY METHOD OF THE SYSTEMS OF EQUATIONS

Certain conditions must be observed before presenting the method:

- This method only applies, *a priori*, to a single solid phase.
- Can be applied to diffractograms obtained by x-ray, neutron or electron techniques.
- Does not consider the diffraction intensities, as the width of the diffracted peaks is narrow and symmetrical; the bases of all peaks are parallel to the 2θ axis of the diffractogram.
- Based on the seven Bravais crystal structures, the number of diffracted peaks (n), the diffraction angles (2θ), and the indexing of each peak (hkl).
- The hkl indices of each crystallographic plane are previously known.
- The diffraction angles 2θ of a diffractogram are taken from their respective intensities.

By knowing a particular structure type and the diffraction angles, the number of lattice parameters (p) to be determined and the interplanar distances can be inferred from the diffraction angles.

With the number n of peaks in the diffractogram, these peaks are combined parameter by parameter, that is, p to p , as follows:

$$C_{n,p} = \frac{n!}{(n-p)!p!} \quad (2)$$

In equation (2), $C_{n,p}$ is the maximum number of combinations of p different lattice parameters chosen among n different peaks and this maximum number represents the number of systems to be solved $p \times p$ from the interplanar distance equations based on the lattice

parameters and hkl indices of the crystallographic plane. For $C_{n,p}$ combinations to be greater than 1, $n > p$ and $p \neq 0$.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{d_{hkl,1}^2} &= \frac{h_1^2 + k_1^2}{a^2} + \frac{l_1^2}{c^2} \\ \frac{1}{d_{hkl,2}^2} &= \frac{h_2^2 + k_2^2}{a^2} + \frac{l_2^2}{c^2} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

In equation 3, the system is 2×2 , that is, $p = 2$, since the parameters to be determined are a and c . In each combination, a value of a and c are determined.

To solve $C_{n,p}$ systems, it is necessary to consider only one hkl plane, among two or more, that have indices other than zero, or when, because one of these indices is equal to zero, it is possible to determine the lattice parameters. For example, let us consider $hk0$ for a tetragonal system (equation 3). With $l = 0$, one can immediately determine the parameter a of the unit cell. The same would occur if we have $00l$ to determine the parameter c . Or, in the orthorhombic structure, if $h00$, $0k0$ or $00l$ occurs, one of the lattice parameters is immediately determined. Therefore, combinations between two or more of these plans must be excluded. The combination of two or more peaks with the same 2θ and different hkl should also be disregarded.

A particular case is for the cubic crystalline system, where $p = 1$, that is, the only parameter to be determined is the edge a and, therefore, there is only a single equation to determine this single lattice parameter, which is $(h^2 + k^2 + l^2)$ as a function of $\sin 2\theta$. The result is $C_{n,1} = n$, that is, there are n ways to select the only parameter a among n peaks. From the set of n hkl planes as a function of n diffraction angles, the parameter a is determined from a linear regression, as the n combinations are independent of each other.

The motivation for developing this method was to extend the determination of lattice parameters beyond the cubic structure in a simpler way.

The method presented here has the advantage of being based on well-founded mathematical concepts such as combinatorial analysis and the system of equations. This makes the determination of lattice parameters more straightforward compared to the Rietveld refinement method, through a relatively simple algorithm. This simplicity arises from the reduced number of variables, as the determination only depends on the diffraction angles, the hkl indices and the number of diffraction peaks. The less symmetrical the crystalline system is, the more equation systems need solving. For example, in the triclinic system there are six unknown parameters ($p = 6$) with $a \neq b \neq c$ and $\alpha \neq \beta \neq \gamma$.

This new method to be applicable was developed in Python programming language and the determination of the lattice parameters is made from an average of the parameters obtained from the resolution of each linear system so that this average is compared with the values obtained from a database. With this new method it is possible to make the determination of lattice parameters more accessible in relation to already established methods.

The objective of this study is to develop a tool in Python and its libraries that allows the determination of the lattice parameters of a known crystal structure in a more direct way. To validate the method, the results of diffractograms of some crystalline compounds provided by previous works will be used. One compound was chosen for each of the seven known crystalline systems. The standard deviation obtained from the results provided by the method

developed here will be evaluated and, together with the averages, the values of lattice parameters will be compared with the reference values of different crystalline systems.

After this description of the method, the next section presents the technique for analytical solution made in Python 3.10 language with brief explanation of the codes. Next, the results for each crystalline system are presented using as a model the structure of the following compounds at room temperature and atmospheric pressure: Y_2O_3 , SnO_2 , SrCO_3 , ZnO , Fe_2O_3 , SrSiO_3 and $\text{Mg}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ [23] arranged from most symmetrical to most less symmetrical. Finally, the results will be compared and discussed with those in the literature.

TECHNIQUE BASED ON PYTHON LANGUAGE

For information on diffractograms, the Inorganic Crystal Structure Database (ICSD) [23] was considered with $\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$ with a step of 0.01° in the range between 10° and 80° , for substances at temperature and pressure atmospheric.

The codes for solving the lattice parameters were written with software PyCharm 2022.3.2 (Community Edition), Runtime version 17.0.5+1-b653.25 amd64 (Powered by open-source software; Copyright© 2010-2024 Jet Brains s.r.o). The libraries used were *math*, *scipy.optimize*, *numpy as np*, *sympy as np* e *itertools*.

Initially, the following code was written for the cubic system, which is the simplest among the seven crystalline systems.

```
def resultado_angulos(estrutura, picos, distancias, comp_de_onda, h, k, l, a, media_a):
    print(estrutura)
    print("Ângulo | 2-Theta | distância interplanar | h k l | a ")
    angulo = 0
    for pico in picos:
        print(" ", angulo, " ", pico, " ", '{:.{}f}'.format(round((distancias[angulo]), 6), 6),
              " ", h[angulo],
              " ", k[angulo], l[angulo], " ", '{:.{}f}'.format(round(a[angulo], 6), 6))
        angulo += 1
    print("Valor médio de a: ", '{:.{}f}'.format(round((media_a), 6), 6), " angstroms")

    desvio = np.std(a)
    print("Desvio-padrão de a: ", '{:.{}f}'.format(round((desvio), 6), 6), " angstroms")
```

Figure 2. Function `resultado_angulos` calculates lattice parameter a for the cubic structure.

The code in Figure 2 defines the function `resultado_angulos`, which outputs information about a crystal structure, including diffraction angles, 2θ peaks, interplanar distances, Miller indices, and values of the lattice parameter a . Additionally, it calculates and outputs the mean value and standard deviation of the lattice parameter a for the cubic structure. This is a test function designed to create functions for other structures.

The function parameters are:

- `estrutura`: Type or name of the crystalline structure.
- `picos`: List of 2θ angle values.
- `distancias`: List of interplanar distances corresponding to peaks.
- `comp_de_onda`: Wavelength used in the analysis (1.5418 \AA).
- `h, k, l`: Lists of Miller indices corresponding to the peaks.
- `a`: List of lattice parameter a values calculated for each peak.
- `media_a`: Average value of the lattice parameter a .

The **resultado_angulos** function is written to format and display detailed information about diffraction peaks in a crystal structure, including the calculated values of lattice parameters and their statistics. This type of function is useful for analyzing and presenting experimental results in X-ray diffraction and crystallography studies.

A second code was written to determine interplanar distances according to the values of the diffraction angles and the *hkl* indices.

```
def angulos(nome_estrutura):
    picos = []
    h = []
    k = []
    l = []
    distancia = []

    # n = int(input("Digite o número de picos: "))
    comp_de_onda = float(input("Comprimento de onda: "))
    for i in range(n):
        angulo = i
        valor = float(input("Digite o valor do ângulo: "))
        distancia[angulo] = float(comp_de_onda / (2.0 * math.sin(math.radians(valor / 2.0))))
        picos[angulo] = valor
        h[angulo] = int(input("Digite o valor de h: "))
        k[angulo] = int(input("Digite o valor de k: "))
        l[angulo] = int(input("digite o valor de l: "))

    return nome_estrutura, picos, distancia, comp_de_onda, h, k, l
```

Figure 3. Function that allows to calculate the interplanar distance from the *hkl* indices.

The code provided (figure 3) defines a function called **angulos** that asks the user for information about the diffraction peaks of a crystalline structure and returns this organized data. First, it initializes empty lists to store the values of the diffraction angles (**picos**), the Miller indices (**h**, **k**, **l**) and the interplanar distances (**distancia**). It then asks the user for the wavelength used in the analysis and converts the input to a floating-point number (**float**). And finally, it returns a tuple containing the name of the structure, the list of peaks, the list of interplanar distances, the wavelength and the lists of Miller indices.

```
print(
    " 1- Cúbica\n 2- Tetragonal\n 3- Ortorrômbica\n 4- Hexagonal\n 5- Romboédrica\n 6- Monoclinica\n 7- Triclinica")
opcao = int(input("Digite tipo de estrutura: "))

if opcao == 1:
    cubica()
elif opcao == 2:
    tetragonal()
elif opcao == 3:
    ortorrômbica()
elif opcao == 4:
    hexagonal()
elif opcao == 5:
    romboédrica()
elif opcao == 6:
    monoclinica()
elif opcao == 7:
    triclinica()
else:
    print("Opção inválida. Por favor, escolha uma opção válida.")
```

Figure 4. Option to choose a structure to determine the lattice parameters.

For each crystal structure, a function was constructed with the instruction **def** (figure 4) followed by the name of the structure. With the function **def angulos(nome_estrutura)** it was possible to determine the interplanar distances for each diffraction angle, so that the interplanar distance was defined as a vector.

Instead of entering the 2θ angles and hkl values, these previously known values were defined for each compound as a model for the calculations. The user must enter the type of structure and wavelength. Automatically the algorithm determines the lattice parameters.

In the case of solving the cubic structure (figure 5), the following code was used and the structural data of yttrium oxide as a model.

```
def cubica():
    a = []
    media = float(0)

    #Y2O3 - óxido de ítrio
    picos = [16.71, 20.51, 23.72, 29.16, 31.56, 33.8, 35.92, 37.93, 39.86, 41.71, 43.5, 46.91, 48.55, 50.14, 51.7,
            53.23,
            54.72, 56.19, 57.64, 59.06, 60.46, 61.84, 63.21, 64.56, 65.89, 69.81]
    h = [2, 1, 2, 2, 1, 0, 4, 0, 3, 2, 1, 5, 4, 4, 0, 3, 0, 5, 2, 1, 4, 5, 0, 5, 0, 1]
    k = [0, 1, 0, 2, -3, 4, -1, 2, 2, 2, 3, 2, 0, 3, 0, 5, -2, -1, -0, -0, -4, -4, 0, -5, -4, 5]
    l = [0, 2, 2, 2, 2, 0, -1, 4, -3, 4, -4, -1, -4, 3, 0, 2, 0, -4, 2, 3, -4, 3, -4, -2, -2, 0]

    conta = 0
    # nome_estrutura, picos, distancia, comp_de_onda, h, k, l = angulos("Estrutura Cúbica")
    nome_estrutura, distancias, comp_de_onda = angulosFeste(picos)
    for distancia in distancias:
        a.append(distancia * (math.sqrt((h[conta] ** 2) + (k[conta] ** 2) + (l[conta] ** 2))))
        media = media + a[conta]
        conta += 1

    media = media / conta
    print(media)
    desvio = np.std(a)
    print("Desvio-padrão de a: ", '{:.{}}f'.format(round((desvio), 6), 6), " angstroms")
    resultado_angulos(nome_estrutura, picos, distancias, comp_de_onda, h, k, l, a, media)
    print("angulo_alfa = angulo_beta = angulo_gama = 90 graus")
```

Figure 5. Function for cubic structure.

From the tetragonal system (figure 6) and other systems, combinations of peaks were used.

```
ctCombina = 1;
tamanhoPicos = len(picos)
# tamanhoPicos = 9
indices = list(range(tamanhoPicos))
combinacoes_indices = list(itertools.combinations(indices, 2))
for combinacao in combinacoes_indices:
    angulo1 = combinacao[0]
    angulo2 = combinacao[1]
    s_combina = str(ctCombina) + ": " + str(picos[angulo1]) + " e " + str(picos[angulo2])
    ctCombina += 1
    print(s_combina)
```

Figure 6. Combination of peaks n to n to resolve systems for $n > 1$, where n is the number of parameters to be determined. In this case, $n = 2$ for the tetragonal system.

The code in figure 7 applies to the tetragonal structure. Each combination of peaks represents a system of equations to be solved based on the equations of each structure where the interplanar distance, lattice parameters and hkl indices are related.

```

# Definindo as variáveis simbólicas x e y
x, y = sp.symbols('x y')

# Definindo as equações
equation1 = sp.Eq(((h[angulo1]** 2 + (k[angulo1]** 2)) / (x** 2)) + ((l[angulo1]** 2) / (y** 2)),
                 1 / (distancia[angulo1]** 2))

equation2 = sp.Eq(
    ((h[angulo2]** 2 + (k[angulo2]** 2)) / (x** 2)) + ((l[angulo2]** 2) / (y** 2)),
    1 / (distancia[angulo2]** 2))

# Resolvendo o sistema de equações
solution = sp.solve((equation1, equation2), (x, y))
if len(solution) != 0:
    a.append(float(solution[3][0]))
    c.append(float(solution[3][1]))
    media_a = media_a + solution[3][0]
    media_c = media_c + solution[3][1]
    # cont += 1
    conta += 1
# print("Solução do sistema de equações:")
# print(solution)

# for i in range(len(a)):
#     print("a" + str(i) + ":" + str(a[i]) + " a" + str(i) + ":" + str(a[i]) + " c" + str(i) + ":" + str(c[i]))
media_a = media_a / conta
media_c = media_c / conta

print("Tetragonal")
print("Ângulo | 2-Theta | distância interplanar | h k l ")

for i in range(tamanhoPicos):
    angulo = i
    valor = picos[angulo]
    print(" ", angulo + 1, " ", valor, " ", '{:.{}}'.format(round((distancia[angulo]), 6), 6),
          " ", " ", " ", h[angulo], k[angulo], l[angulo])

for i in range(len(a)):
    print("a" + str(i + 1) + ":" + str(a[i]) + " c" + str(i + 1) + ":" + str(
        c[i]))

print("Valor médio de a: ", '{:.{}}'.format(round((media_a), 6), 6), " angstroms")
# valores = list(a.values())
desvio = np.std(a)
print("Desvio-padrão de a: ", '{:.{}}'.format(round((desvio), 6), 6), " angstroms")

print("Valor médio de c: ", '{:.{}}'.format(round((media_c), 6), 6), " angstroms")
desvio = np.std(c)
print("Desvio-padrão de c: ", '{:.{}}'.format(round((desvio), 6), 6), " angstroms")
print("angulo_alfa = angulo_beta = angulo_gama = 90 graus")

```

Figure 7. Function for solving systems of equations for the tetragonal structure using `sp.solve`.

Figure 7 presents the code `sp.solve((equation1, equation2), (x, y))` to solve systems of two equations. The difference between this tetragonal structure code and the others is the number of equations and variables and the structure equation that relates the interplanar distance with the *hkl* indices and the lattice parameters. For example, in the orthorhombic structure, as there are three parameters to be determined, the program combines the peaks 3 by 3, so that each combination results in a 3 by 3 system. Each solved system provides a value

of a , b and c . In the end, the mean and standard deviation of each lattice parameter are determined.

In the case of the trigonal structure, the same code as the hexagonal structure was used and this in turn is like the tetragonal one.

For the triclinic system, we first used a part of the code already used in other systems to calculate the coefficients S_{11}/V^2 , S_{22}/V^2 , S_{33}/V^2 , S_{12}/V^2 , S_{23}/V^2 and S_{13}/V^2 of the interplanar distance equation,^[2] where V is the volume of the unit cell and the coefficients are designated by x , y , z , w , n , m , respectively. S_{11} , S_{22} , S_{33} , S_{12} , S_{23} and S_{13} depend on the lattice parameters in quadratic forms and the sines and cosines of the angles. For this reason, determining parameters as in other systems is unfeasible for the triclinic structure.

The expressions of S_{11} , S_{22} , S_{33} , S_{12} , S_{23} and S_{13} were combined to eliminate V^2 between them and the lattice parameters a , b and c . The result was the reduction of six equations to three non-linear equations whose equality provides a relationship between the values of the coefficients determined before and the cosines of the angles α , β , γ .

From these three new equations, the triclinic system code uses the *least_squares* function from the *scipy.optimize* module to solve systems of nonlinear equations. Figure 8 defines the equations for the triclinic system.

```
# Definindo as equações para os parâmetros de rede
equation7 = sp.Eq(((1 - r1 ** 2) ** 0.5 / (1 - r3 ** 2) ** 0.5) * (r2 * r3 - r1) / (r1 * r2 - r3),
                 (solution[n] / solution[w]) * (solution[x] / solution[z]) ** 0.5)
equation8 = sp.Eq(((1 - r1 ** 2) ** 0.5 / (1 - r2 ** 2) ** 0.5) * (r2 * r3 - r1) / (r3 * r1 - r2),
                 (solution[n] / solution[m]) * (solution[x] / solution[y]) ** 0.5)
equation9 = sp.Eq(((1 - r2 ** 2) ** 0.5 / (1 - r3 ** 2) ** 0.5) * (r3 * r1 - r2) / (r1 * r2 - r3),
                 (solution[m] / solution[w]) * (solution[y] / solution[z]) ** 0.5)
```

Figure 8. Definition of equations.

Figure 9 represents the conversion of equations to lambda functions.

```
# Convertendo as equações para uma função lambda para uso com least_squares
f7 = sp.lambdify((r1, r2, r3), equation7.lhs - equation7.rhs, "numpy")
f8 = sp.lambdify((r1, r2, r3), equation8.lhs - equation8.rhs, "numpy")
f9 = sp.lambdify((r1, r2, r3), equation9.lhs - equation9.rhs, "numpy")
```

Figure 9. Conversion of equations to lambda functions.

A function was then created that groups the equations (figure 10).

```
def equations(vars):
    r1, r2, r3 = vars
    return [f7(r1, r2, r3), f8(r1, r2, r3), f9(r1, r2, r3)]
```

Figure 10. Grouping of equations.

The variables $r1$, $r2$ and $r3$ represent $\cos\alpha$, $\cos\beta$ and $\cos\gamma$, respectively.

Lambda functions are anonymous functions, that is, functions defined without a name, which are generally used for simple expressions. In the context of solving systems of equations, the lambda function is used to convert symbolic expressions into numeric functions that can be evaluated with specific data.^[24]

The disadvantage here is that we must previously know the angles from the triclinic system database to provide the code (figure 11). For other structures, it is not necessary to know any parameters in advance.

From these values provided by the user, a function is created to adjust the angle values, keeping the ratios between the cosines of the angles constant.

```
# Razões constantes entre r1, r2 e r3
deg1 = float(input("Digite o ângulo alfa: "))
deg2 = float(input("Digite o ângulo beta: "))
deg3 = float(input("Digite o ângulo gama: "))
razao_r1_r2 = np.cos(np.radians(deg1)) / np.cos(np.radians(deg2))
razao_r2_r3 = np.cos(np.radians(deg2)) / np.cos(np.radians(deg3))

# Função para ajustar os ângulos mantendo as razões constantes
def ajustar_angulo(vars):
    angulo_alfa, angulo_beta = vars
    r1 = np.cos(np.radians(angulo_alfa))
    r2 = r1 / razao_r1_r2
    r3 = r2 / razao_r2_r3
    return [r1, r2, r3]
```

Figure 11. Constant ratios and function to adjust angles to keep ratios constant.

An objective function (figure 12) is defined to evaluate the error of the equations based on the adjusted angles. The *differential_evolution* method is used to find the best initial angles, minimizing the objective function.

```
# Função objetivo para minimizar
def objective_function(angles):
    r1, r2, r3 = ajustar_angulo(angles)
    return np.sum(np.square(equations([r1, r2, r3])))

# Usando differential_evolution para encontrar os melhores ângulos iniciais
bounds = [(0, 180), (0, 180)]
result_angles = differential_evolution(objective_function, bounds)

# Ajustando os ângulos encontrados
r1, r2, r3 = ajustar_angulo(result_angles.x)
```

Figure 12. Objective function.

The objective function^[25] $F(r_1, r_2, r_3)$ is the sum of the squares of the residuals of the equations: $F(r_1, r_2, r_3) = f_1(r_1, r_2, r_3)^2 + f_2(r_1, r_2, r_3)^2 + f_3(r_1, r_2, r_3)^2$. Here, f_1 , f_2 and f_3 are the residuals of the equations. Minimizing $F(r_1, r_2, r_3)$ involves finding the values of r_1 , r_2 and r_3 that make the residues f_1 , f_2 and f_3 as close to zero as possible. Ideally, if $F(r_1, r_2, r_3) = 0$, it means that r_1 , r_2 and r_3 are exact solutions to the system of equations. To minimize $F(r_1, r_2, r_3)$, numerical methods such as Levenberg-Marquardt or Newton-Raphson can be used. These methods iterate from an initial estimate of the values of r_1 , r_2 and r_3 and adjust these values to minimize the objective function.

The *least_squares* function is used to solve the system of equations (figure 13). This function minimizes the sum of the squares of the differences between the system's equations,

which is the objective function, resulting in the values r_1 , r_2 and r_3 that satisfy the original equations.

```
# Usando least_squares para refinar os valores
def refined_equations(vars):
    return equations(vars)

initial_guess = [r1, r2, r3]
result = least_squares(refined_equations, initial_guess, bounds=(-1, 1))
```

Figure 13. Use the least squares method (`least_squares`).

From each set of coefficients (S_{11}/V^2 , S_{22}/V^2 , S_{33}/V^2 , S_{12}/V^2 , S_{23}/V^2 and S_{13}/V^2) a set of lattice parameters is determined and, finally, the average and the standard deviation of each parameter.

The Python scripts and datasets used in this study are publicly available at our GitHub repository: <http://github.com/JonesSoares1980/lattice-parameters>.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Let's test some conditions regarding peak selection for the generated codes. Initially, the selected peaks were those without repeated 2θ angles for different hkl indices, chosen randomly.

The SymPy library's `sp.solve` method does not directly use Cramer's method or the scaling method (Gaussian elimination) but uses a more general approach to solving systems of algebraic equations, which may involve a combination of symbolic computer algebra techniques.

SymPy can apply different methods depending on the nature of the given system of equations. Among these methods we can mention symbolic substitution, Gaussian elimination,^[26] Newton's method for nonlinear systems,^[27] Gröbner's method for solving systems of polynomial equations,^[28] among others.^{[29],[30]}

The computational complexity of calculating determinants for an $n \times n$ matrix is $O(n!)O(n!)$, which is impractical for large n , particularly for the triclinic system due to the complexity of its equation for the calculation of the interplanar distance based on the lattice parameters and the Miller index of the crystallographic plane.

Calculations in Python were initially performed using an Intel® Core™ i3 processor. The time to determine the lattice parameters depends on the processor used, the number of peaks considered, the structural complexity and the technique for solving systems of equations.

Table 1 presents the time required to determine the lattice parameters according to the number of peaks and the combinations made for $\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$. The number of combinations made is the number of measurements of each lattice parameter.

Table 1 was created just to get an idea of the relationship between the maximum number of combinations and the number of combinations made, and the execution time of the calculations. Calculation time may vary depending on structural complexity and number of peaks.

Table 1. Average time to determine lattice parameters according to the number of selected peaks.

Compound	Structure	Number of Peaks*	Maximum combination	Number of combinations made	Time (seconds)
Y ₂ O ₃	Cubic	449	449	449	0.89
SnO ₂	Tetragonal	13	78	68	8.99
SrCO ₃	Ortorrombic	66	45780	42373	32438
ZnO	Hexagonal	10	45	42	9.36
Fe ₂ O ₃	Trigonal	22	231	225	29.96
SrSiO ₃	Monoclinic	7	35	15	1835
Mg ₃ (PO ₄) ₂	Triclinic	14	3003	613	960

* No repetition of 2θ angles.

All possible peaks were selected initially, except for the monoclinic and triclinic structures.

For the cubic structure, all peaks could be considered, as the combinations are independent of each other. For the tetragonal structure, angle 2θ can have, for example, indices $\bar{1}10$ and 110 . Only one of these angles was considered, as two peaks with the same angle cannot combine. Thus, of the total of 51 peaks in the database, only 13 were considered and this was considered for the other structures. In the case of monoclinic and triclinic structures, some peaks were chosen randomly so as not to prolong the calculation time or even exceed the limit of possible combinations within the Python language.

As the structural complexity increases, the number of peaks was reduced, that is, some peaks were selected to make determinations faster. This was done particularly for the monoclinic and triclinic structures so that peaks whose hkl values are $h00$, $0k0$ and $00l$, or $k0l$ and $hk0$ were preferentially considered, to make the calculations faster. With non-zero hkl peaks, the calculation of the system of equations becomes very time-consuming, even with a small number of selected peaks.

Table 2 shows the lattice parameters provided in the literature. Table 3 shows the average lattice parameters determined in Python. For the calculations, the number of peaks illustrated in table 1 was considered. All a , b , and c parameters are in angstroms (\AA) and all α , β , and γ parameters are in degrees ($^\circ$).

Table 2. Referenced parameters from the database.

Compound	Structure	a	b	c	α	β	γ
Y ₂ O ₃	Cubic*	10.6080	10.6080	10.6080			
SnO ₂	Tetragonal	4.7348(1)	4.7348(1)	3.18367(7)			
SrCO ₃	Ortorrombic	5.107499(2)	8.413820(3)	6.026924(2)			
ZnO	Hexagonal	3.2511(2)	3.2511(2)	5.2080(3)			
Fe ₂ O ₃	Trigonal	5.0324(9)	5.0324(9)	13.7643(4)			
SrSiO ₃	Monoclinic	12.328(2)	7.143(1)	10.882(2)		111.58(1)	
Mg ₃ (PO ₄) ₂	Triclinic	8.512(2)	8.982(2)	9.320(3)	116.34(2)	91.50(2)	114.49(2)

* The database does not report the value of the deviations.

Table 3. Lattice parameters calculated in Python from hkl peaks that do not repeat 2θ .

Compound	Structure	a	b	c	α	β	γ
Y ₂ O ₃	Cubic	10.6079(6)	10.6079(6)	10.6079(6)			
SnO ₂	Tetragonal	4.7347(8)	4.7347(8)	3.184(2)			
SrCO ₃	Ortorrombic	5.11(1)	8.41(2)	6.03(1)			
ZnO	Hexagonal	3.2511(2)	3.2511(2)	5.2080(2)			
Fe ₂ O ₃	Trigonal	5.032(2)	5.032(2)	13.76(2)			
SrSiO ₃	Monoclinic	12.325(4)	7.1430(5)	10.879(4)		111.56(2)	
Mg ₃ (PO ₄) ₂	Triclinic	8.49930(2)	8.96551(3)	9.31374(2)	116.3005(2)	91.5265(1)	114.3568(2)

The average values of the lattice parameters were compared as well as the standard deviations.

The method developed here demonstrates that the average lattice parameter values determined in Python are very close to those in the database. The percentage difference was made between the average values considering the same number of decimal places.

The biggest difference occurs in relation to parameters a , b , and γ of the triclinic system (0.15, 0.18 and 0.11%, respectively) and after parameters a and c of the orthorhombic system (0.05%). The biggest difference also occurs in the parameter c of the tetragonal and trigonal systems whose differences are 0.01% and 0.03%, respectively, and in the parameter β of the monoclinic system whose difference is 0.018%.

The smallest difference occurs for the hexagonal ZnO system whose mean values and deviations are identical followed by the cubic system.

In relation to deviations, the method developed here appears, in general, to be greater in relation to the values in the database. This is because all possible peaks were used except for the monoclinic and triclinic systems. The largest standard deviation is observed in the orthorhombic system, while the smallest deviation is found in the hexagonal system, followed by the cubic system

If we compare only the average values of the lattice parameters determined in Python with the database values, they are similar with a difference of 0 (for the hexagonal system) up to 0.02% (parameters a , c and β of the monoclinic system).

Comparing the values of the lattice parameters for the triclinic system in tables 2 and 3 we see that the percentage differences vary from 0.011% for angle β to 0.075% for parameter c .

Table 4 shows the results for the selected most intense peaks. For the cubic, tetragonal, orthorhombic, hexagonal and trigonal systems, peaks with relative intensity between 70 and 1000 were considered. For the monoclinic structure, only 7 of the most intense peaks were considered so that the combinations resulted in solutions of the lattice parameters. For the triclinic system, 14 of the most intense peaks were considered.

Table 4. Lattice parameters calculated in Python from the most intense peaks.

Compound	Structure	<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	α	β	γ
Y ₂ O ₃	Cubic	10.6077(3)	10.6077(3)	10.6077(3)			
SnO ₂	Tetragonal	4.7348(6)	4.7348(6)	3.1836(9)			
SrCO ₃	Ortorrombic	5.107(4)	8.414(6)	6.027(4)			
ZnO	Hexagonal	3.2511(2)	3.2511(2)	5.2082(6)			
Fe ₂ O ₃	Trigonal	5.033(2)	5.033(2)	13.764(5)			
SrSiO ₃	Monoclinic	12.3277(1)	7.1430(2)	10.881(1)		111.572(1)	
Mg ₃ (PO ₄) ₂	Triclinic	8.508680(2)	8.980927(5)	9.315557(3)	116.32934(3)	91.50467(2)	114.46249(3)

In general, an improvement in the precision of the results in table 4 is observed in relation to the results in table 3 when considering the most intense peaks.

From table 4 it can be seen that the cubic structure presents a smaller deviation, but a slightly lower average value in relation to the values in tables 2 and 3. For the tetragonal system, although the value of *a* is identical to that in table 2, the deviation -standard is higher and for parameter *c* the precision is lower in relation to the values in tables 2 and 3.

In the case of the orthorhombic system, the lattice parameters present improved precision, but still lower in relation to the values in table 2.

For the hexagonal structure, the parameter *a* maintained its precision and the parameter *c* is slightly larger with a standard deviation also larger.

For the trigonal structure, parameter *a* maintained its accuracy while parameter *c* had its accuracy increased.

The monoclinic structure not only improved in precision but also surpassed the values in table 2 in terms of precision and standard deviation.

Finally, the triclinic structure presented mean values of lattice parameters that were closer and more accurate in relation to the reference values. with differences between 0 and 0.043% in relation to the values in table 2.

This greater precision of lattice parameters when considering the most intense peaks in relation to other peaks generally means that more intense peaks are narrower, in their entirety, in relation to low intensity peaks.

The standard deviations calculated refer to the random errors in the individual calculations of the network parameters from the experimental data provided by the database.

CONCLUSIONS

The combinatory method for determining lattice parameters proved both efficient and accurate. The result provides the maximum number of combinations ($C_{n,p}$), representing the number of $p \times p$ systems to solve, where p is the number of unknown parameters. Not all peak combinations result in lattice parameter solutions.

To solve these systems of equations, the Python programming language and its specific libraries were used. Using this language, it was possible to develop a code for each type of structure. The codes were tested based on experimental data referenced in the database. Except for the triclinic structure, all codes have similar solution techniques with the difference in the number of variables. For the triclinic structure, numerical approximation methods and

the least squares method were used, based on prior knowledge of the angles of this structure from the database.

Comparing only the values of the database parameters with the values determined in the Python language, it is observed that the largest difference is 0.18% for parameter b of the triclinic structure and the values are identical in the case of the hexagonal structure. However, the method exhibits higher standard deviations compared to the database values.

Considering only the most intense peaks yields lattice parameters closer to reference values and smaller standard deviations.

The advantages of the method developed here include obtaining lattice parameters more simply and quickly, with values very close to those referenced in the database. The disadvantage is that, as you cannot combine peaks of the same 2θ with different hkl , this reduces the number of combined peaks. In the case of more complicated structures such as monoclinic and triclinic, the reduction in peaks aims to reduce solution time, but can still provide more accurate results.

The combinatorial method applied to diffractograms and implemented in the Python language proved to be effective in determining the lattice parameters for different crystalline systems. Comparisons carried out with existing databases demonstrated that the values obtained are within expectations, validating the proposed methodology.

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